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Research Article

**A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY TO EVALUATE THE
RELATIONSHIP AMONGST VARIOUS TYPES OF TOBACCO
USERS AND RECURRENT APHTHOUS ULCERS**Dr Abdul Rehman Qazi¹, Dr Talha Mahmood², Dr Bilawal Wazir³¹Lahore Medical and Dental College, Lahore, ²Quaid e Azam Medical College Bahawalpur,³Services Institute of Medical Sciences, Lahore.

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Abstract:

Objective: The purpose of our study was to evaluate the relationship amongst various types of tobacco users and recurrent aphthous ulcers.

Study Design: A cross-sectional study.

Place and Duration: This study was conducted at Out Patients Department of Mayo Hospital Lahore for the duration of two months starting from August, 2020 to September, 2020.

Methodology: In our present study we include 500 patients to find out aphthous ulcers. With the help of clinical examination, we collected questionnaire-based data. Qualitative and quantitative variables were including in questionnaire. Type of aphthous ulcers, frequency of recurrence of ulcers, all types of addictive habits (smoking and smokeless tobacco) and medical history are qualitative variables while duration of addiction, age, size of ulcer, duration of ulcer, frequency of addictive habits and no of lesions are quantitative variables. SPSS v.20 was used for the statistical analysis of data. Chi-squared test were also applied.

Results: In our present study we include 500 patients. Addictive habit of smoking tobacco were found in 78 patients. Between these 78 patients, 2 patients (0.4%) were hookah smokers, 75 patients (15%) were cigarette smokers and 1 patient (0.2%) was bidi smoker. Addictive habit of using smokeless tobacco were found in 23 patients. Between these 23 patients, 13 patients (2.6%) were naswar chewers, 7 patients (1.4%) were paan chewers and 3 patients (0.6%) were gutka chewers.

Conclusion: At the end of our study, we conclude that there was no relationship found amongst smoking habits and aphthous ulcers although aphthous ulcers were found lower in smokers as compared with non-smokers.

Key Words: Smokeless, Tobacco Smoking, Aphthous Ulcer, Stomatitis

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INTRODUCTION:

Aphthous ulcer is a common condition, also known as “canker sores” or “aphthous stomatitis”. The term aphthae are derived from Greek word “Aphthi” which means “to set on fire” or “to inflame” [1,2]. It is characterized by the repeated formation of benign and non-contagious ulceration of the oral mucosa membrane [3]. The ulcers present as lesions having yellow ulcerated base surrounded by erythematous halos and covered by fibrino-purulent membrane [4,5,6]. Morbidity of Recurrent Aphthous Ulcer (RAS) is quite high affecting quality of life of patients in a way that they are painful and recurrent mucosal lesions causing discomfort while eating, drinking and speaking. There are three clinical variations of aphthous stomatitis naming Minor aphthous ulceration, major aphthous ulceration and herpetiform aphthous ulceration.

Exact etiology of RAS is unknown but the condition is associated with multiple factors including autoimmunity, genetic predispositions, hematologic abnormalities (anemia), HIV, hormonal fluctuations, arthritis, stress/anxiety, nutritional deficiencies, trauma, drugs, food hypersensitivity, smoking Cessation and allergies [7]. RAS is associated with human leukocyte antigen (HLA) and immune-dysregulation. Lymphocytes are the predominant cells in pathogenesis of RAS with a variation in CD4:CD8 ratio during pre-ulceration, ulceration, and healing stage. Tobacco reduces Immunity and T cell response to various antigens so that the association appears to be biologically Plausible [8]. The management of patients with RAS comprises application of topical analgesics, corticosteroids, antibiotics and anti-inflammatory agents that only provide symptomatic relief. There are different types of tobacco being used in Pakistan which includes smoking tobacco i.e., Cigarettes, cigar, pipe, hookah, shisha and bidi and smokeless tobacco include paan, gutka, naswar, oral snuff, snuss (moist snuff), khaini (tobacco and lime) and lozenges.

Although studies have failed to find the exact etiology of Recurrent Aphthous Stomatitis but tobacco use is the one most debatable and confused anticipated factor as tobacco usage is associated with various oral pathologies such as Oral squamous cell carcinoma, periodontitis, gingivitis, tobacco pouch keratosis, oral sub mucous fibrosis and nicotine stomatitis etc., so tobacco usage should logically lead to occurrence of Recurrent Aphthous Stomatitis. However, in contrast to this a number of studies have shown negative correlation between RAS and tobacco usage and positive therapeutic effects of smoking. Tobacco

usage causes thickening (keratinization) of oral mucosa which renders the mucosa less susceptible to ulceration. Smokers quitting with nicotine chewing gums have less chances to develop ulcers than those without nicotine replacement therapy [9].

Previous studies have suggested negative association between tobacco usage and RAU but most of those studies assessed relationship between RAS and tobacco by using methods that were based on interviews, questionnaire, or on self-reporting of Smoking status [10,11]. However, the studies that were previously carried out did not evaluate occurrence of aphthous ulcers in different forms of tobacco users, mixed habits and non-users. In our study we wanted to evaluate the strength of association between occurrence of aphthous ulcer and tobacco usage and incidence of aphthous ulcer among different types of tobacco users in our population and comparing them with non-users because no such study has been done in our community.

METHODOLOGY:

This cross-sectional study was conducted at Out Patients Department of Mayo Hospital Lahore for the duration of two months starting from August, 2020 to September, 2020. Study was conducted on 500 patients who visited OPD of hospital for seeking dental treatment. All subjects were interviewed and a structured questionnaire was developed to record their details. The questionnaire contained four main sections (addictive habits/tobacco usage history, aphthous ulcer related medical history, ulcer characteristics and demographics). The Addictive habits section had two domains; Smoking tobacco domain comprised of six tobacco usage habits (smoking cigarettes, cigar, hookah, pipe, shisha, bidi) and Smokeless tobacco domain also had six habits (paan, ghutka, naswar, snuff, lozenges, other habits).

Medical history associated with the occurrence of aphthous ulcers included Anemia, HIV, Hormonal fluctuations, GI disorders, Arthritis, Stress/anxiety, Allergies and genetic predisposition. Ulcer characteristics comprised size of ulcer, number of lesions, site of ulceration, frequency of recurrence and duration of ulcers. Informed Consent was taken from all the participants before conducting the study. The participants were asked whether they had oral ulcers (aphthous ulcers) present in their mouth after describing aphthosis to them as recurrent painful ulcers. Additional information about ulcers like duration, location, size, recurrence, and no. of ulcers was noted.

Moreover, risk factors that might be related to condition were inquired (stress, hormonal factors, GD disorders, allergies). Participants were classified into 3 groups: control group, smoker group and non-smoker group, in control group inclusion criteria included male and female of 15 years and above, subjecting without any ulcers and without any addictive habits, exclusion criteria included patients under 15 years, subjecting with ulcers and with addictive habits. In smoker group inclusion criteria included male and female patients of 15 years and above, subjecting with smoking habits (Cigarette, cigar, pipe, hookah, shisha, bidi) and with/without ulcers, exclusion criteria included patients under 15-year subjecting without any smoking habits. In non-smokers group inclusion criteria included male and female patients of 15 years and above, subjecting without any smoking habits, with smokeless tobacco habits (paan, gutka, naswar, snuff, lozenges) and with/without ulcers, exclusion criteria included patients less than 15 years, subjecting with smoking habits and without any smokeless tobacco habits.

To assess the presence of aphthous ulcers, oral mucosal examination and questionnaire were completed for 500 patients reporting to the OPD over a 2-month interval by four examiners. History of addictive habits was taken and tobacco usage was measured on the basis of type of tobacco used, frequency of consumption per day and the duration for

which the individual maintained this frequency. To avoid confounding, patients with known history of systemic diseases and other conditions that might influence occurrence of aphthous ulcer were also recorded. And finally, on the basis of ulcer characteristics, aphthous ulcerations were categorized into minor, major and herpetiform ulcers. Statistical analysis was carried out using SPSS software version 20.

Qualitative and quantitative variables were including in questionnaire. Type of aphthous ulcers, frequency of recurrence of ulcers, all types of addictive habits (smoking and smokeless tobacco) and medical history are qualitative variables while duration of addiction, age, size of ulcer, duration of ulcer, frequency of addictive habits and no of lesions are quantitative variables.

RESULTS:

All 500 subjects were asked about their medical histories. Out of 500, only 5 subjects (1%) were anemic. 10 subjects (2%) had hormonal disorders related with puberty, menstrual cycle and pregnancy, 83 subjects (16.6%) had GI disorders related to acidity, 7 subjects (1.4%) had arthritis, 74 subjects (14.8) experienced stress related Ulcerations during exams or social issues. 61 subjects (12.2%) were allergic to dust, pollen and medications, and 5 subjects (1%) presented with family history of recurrent ulcers.

Table No 01: Self-Reported Medical History of Patients

Medical History	Qty	%age	Total
Anemia	5	1%	500
Hormonal	10	2%	500
GI disorder	83	16.6%	500
Arthritis	7	1.4%	500
Stress	74	14.8%	500
Allergies	61	12.2%	500
Genetics	5	1%	500

Out of 500 subjects, 78 subjects had addictive habits of smoking tobacco. Among those 78, Cigarette Smokers were 75 (15%), Hookah Smokers were 2 (0.4%) and 1 was a Bidi Smoker (0.2%).

Table No 02: Addictive Habits of Smoking Tobacco

Smoking Type	Qty	%age
Cigarette	75	15%
Hookah	2	0.4%
Bidi	1	0.2%
Total	78	15.6%

From 500 subjects, 23 subjects had addictive habits of using smokeless tobacco. And of those 23, Paan Chewers were 7 (1.4%), Gutka Chewers were 3 (0.6%) and 13 were Naswar Chewers (2.6%).

Table No 03: Addictive Habit of Using Smokeless Tobacco

Smokeless Tobacco	Qty	%age
Paan	7	1.4%
Gutka	3	0.6%
Naswar	13	2.6%
Total	23	4.6%

From a group of 101 subjects that presented with addictive habits of either smoking or smokeless tobacco 46 were addicted for more than a period of 7 years.

Table No 04: Illustrates Distribution of Duration of Addiction Among Addicts

Duration of addiction	Qty	%age
Less than 2 years	8	1.6%
2-5 years	22	4.4%
5-7 years	25	5%
7-10 years	12	2.4%
More than 10 years	34	6.8%
Total	101	2.02%

Duration of Tobacco Addict on 33 (6.6%) participants presented with aphthous ulcers. Pertaining to the ulcer characteristics, 2 patients presented with Major Aphthous Ulceration and 31 patients presented with Minor Aphthous Ulcerations. None of the patients presented with Herpetiform Aphthous Ulcerations during the period of sample collection. And out of these 33 subjects who presented with aphthous ulcers,

5 were cigarette smokers while remaining 28 had no history of any addictive habits (smoking or smokeless tobacco). Presence of aphthous ulcers was correlated with self-reported medical conditions; 5 out of 33 subjects (15.1%) were allergic, 9 (27.2%) had GI disorders, 3 (9%) had hormonal disorders, 12 (36.4%) had stress-related ulcers, 4 (12.1%) had genetic association and 6 (18.2%) subjects presented without

any significant medical history. Occurrence of RAU is affected by a number of other variables, with no statistically significant influence of tobacco usage.

Table No 05: Ulcer Characteristics

Ulcer Characteristics	Variables	Qty	%age
Duration	5-7 days	3	0.6%
	7-14 days	28	5.6%
	2-6 weeks	2	0.4%
	Total	33	6.6%
No of Lesions	1-5	30	6%
	5-10	2	0.4%
	10-100	1	0.2%
	Total	33	6.6%
Frequency of Recurrence	Non-Recurrent	4	0.8%
	Recur Frequently	25	5%
	Recur Rarely	4	0.8%
	Total	33	6.6%
Site of Ulceration	Non- keratinized	25	5%
	Keratinized	8	8%
	Total	33	6.6%
Size of Individual Lesions	1-3 mm	21	4.2%
	3-10 mm	10	2%
	3 cm	2	0.4%
	Total	33	6.6%
Total		500	100%

Incidence of RAU in tobacco users and non-users was statistically analyzed by using Chi-squared test. Cigarette smoking was considered to represent tobacco usage as significant number of tobacco users were cigarette smokers as compared with negligible amount of other tobacco variables. Cigarette smoking was compared with presence of RAU and type of ulcers if present. Statistical analysis of our study showed no significant association between the presence of aphthous ulcers and cigarette smoking (p value = 0.98) and between cigarette smoking and type of aphthous ulcers (p value = 0.72)

Table No 06: Relationship of Cigarette Smoking with Aphthous Ulcer

Type of Ulcer	Cigarette Smoking	
	Yes	No
Minor Aphthous Ulcers	5	26
Major Aphthous Ulcers	0	2

DISCUSSION:

Aphthous ulcers are recurrent and painful condition of oral mucosa, etiology of which is still unknown [3]. There are certain risk factors that are associated with occurrence of RAU including immune reaction, genetic factors, hormonal factors, stress, infections, GI disorders etc. No randomized control trial has shown

any treatment, that could help in preventing or curing RAU [4].

An inverse relationship is observed between RAU frequency and smoking habits according to previous studies held [3,5,9]. The observations previously made by Tony Axell and Vingent Henricsson also presents

that there is a negative association between tobacco habits and RAU. According to them, surface structures like leukoedema and keratin prevent the penetration of antigenic substances into the oral epithelium [9]. Shapiro et al. Found that there is a negative relation between RAU and smoking. They pointed that genetic, familial, psychological and environmental factors are important considerations in the formation of recurrent aphthous ulceration. They suggest that meaningful data can be obtained by multidisciplinary longitudinal studies. According to Banoczy and Sallay there is a negative association between keratinization of oral mucosa and aphthae [12].

The findings of the case control study given by PA Atkin, X Xu, and MH Thornhill indicate that patients with RAU have low levels of smoking than in matched controls, and they support that there is a negative correlation between minor RAU and smoking. The negative correlation of smokeless tobacco with recurrent aphthous stomatitis is also given in a study by Grady et al. The case control study 3 given by Shamaz Mohamed and Chandrashekar Janakiram found the statistical association between the RAU and usage of tobacco smoking. The association that exists between smoking and aphthous mouth ulcers is negative. The non- tobacco users tend to have 55% more chance of occurrence of RAU than tobacco users. However, study carried out by Slebioda Z and Dorocka, showed there is no significant association found between smoking tobacco habits and Occurrence of Recurrent Aphthous ulcers [13].

Epidemiological studies suggest a protective effect of smoking. These studies show that mouth ulcers are more common in nonsmokers than in smokers [14,15]. The reason that might be associated with this protective effect of tobacco use could be increased keratinization of oral mucous membrane or some substances present in cigarette smoke absorbed causing decrease in frequency of RAU. Case studies suggest that the nicotine chewing gums are helpful for the nonsmokers who have mouth ulcers [16]. Most of the population, on cessation of smoking appear to develop RAU for the first time or any previous RAU that existed, has exacerbated. This might possibly be due to increased keratinization of oral mucosa, antibacterial effect of tobacco smoke [17,18] or smoking cessation have effects on immune system like stress generated due to withdrawal.

Most of these previous studies assessed relationship between RAU and tobacco by using methods that were based on interviews, questionnaires, or on self-

reporting of smoking status [3,10,11]. Our study also used the same method as special questionnaire was designed according to which significantly smaller population of RAU patients were smokers (15%) as compared to control group who were nonsmokers (84.4%) in a sample of 500 patients. Most of the incidences of RAU were found among sample population who were non tobacco users. Some daily tobacco habits were found in patients among which smoking was most common habit especially cigarette smoking while some in rest of the sample were addicted to other forms of tobacco (smoking and smokeless) and no ulcers were found among them. In contrast to other studies [13,5,15] our study showed no significant association between presence of ulcers and cigarette smoking and no association between cigarette smoking and type of ulcers.

CONCLUSION:

At the end of our study, we conclude that there was no relationship found amongst smoking habits and aphthous ulcers although aphthous ulcers were found lower in smokers as compared with non-smokers. However, no significant association has been found between ulcer occurrence and smoking habits. These findings substantiate with the previous similar studies and can serve as a base for further research in future.

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